

Evaluation of the CIPP Model Information and Communication Technology Guidance Program

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Abstract— *The purpose of this study was to find out the application of the ICT Guidance program using the CIPP Model, knowing the effectiveness of the guidance process and knowing student learning outcomes. Determination of the effectiveness of a guidance process is seen from how much the level of achievement of the guidance objectives that have been determined at the beginning of the activity. This research is a qualitative research that uses the CIPP model by evaluating each component of the context, inputs, processes and products to achieve an effective guidance process. The research data sources were students, ICT guidance teachers, curriculum representatives, and Principals in the Padang City Public Middle School. Primary data collection uses observation instruments while secondary data is obtained through documentation and interviews. The data from the observations obtained were then analyzed quantitatively while the data from the documentation and interviews were analyzed qualitatively. From the results of the study, the implementation of guidance which includes the requirements for the implementation of guidance and guidance activities was quite effective.*

Keywords— *Evaluasi, Bimbingan TIK, CIPP.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Entering the 21st century competition and challenges in all aspects of life are getting bigger. Increasingly advanced technology and a rapidly expanding free market encourage the availability of reliable and quality human resources. Human resources are said to be reliable and quality if they have the ability or skill that can encourage them to progress and continue to develop. In order to become a reliable and quality human resource, one must have 21st century skills.

Related to this, education is one of the fields that have an important role in creating human resources that have 21st century skills. In the Partnership for 21st Century Skills it is said that 21st century capabilities include (a) critical thinking and problem solving or critical thinking and problem solving, (b) communication and collaboration or communicating and collaborating, (c) creativity and innovation or creativity and innovation. These skills must be possessed by someone in order to compete with the outside world. Therefore, the world of education must be able to provide learning that can develop 21st century skills.

Therefore, human resources need to be prepared in order to be able to master and develop technology well. 21st century competition requires students to have better knowledge and skills. Understanding of the concept of a material is one indicator of achieving better student knowledge. This is what

causes the world of Education to be required to create a structure of the Education system that can prepare students to live effectively in the 21st century.

The Indonesian education world can see that there are still frequent curriculum changes, such as the current curriculum in the 2013 curriculum. This curriculum is a curriculum development that has been there before. The existence of curriculum changes in Indonesia is inseparable from the changing times that are increasingly developing, simultaneously the curriculum must adjust it (Fadhillah, 2014: 17)^[1].

Curriculum 2013 is a component used in the educational process where the assessment contained in the curriculum includes knowledge, skills and attitudes competencies. 2013 curriculum development is directed at achieving competencies that have been formulated from Graduation Standards (SKL). The formulation of the 2013 curriculum starts with establishing graduate competency standards based on the readiness of students and national education goals. 2013 curriculum was established as an educational organizing tool for the first time in 2013/2014 where as a new curriculum concept, a curriculum that cannot be applied universally and quickly, so there are still few schools that implement the 2013 curriculum.

The state junior high schools in the city of Padang have made several preparations to implement the 2013 curriculum. This can be seen from the facilities, infrastructure and supporting learning resources and some efforts that have been taken by the teachers. Teachers at the Public Middle School in the City of Padang have shared their efforts to succeed in implementing the 2013 curriculum by participating in training activities on curriculum implementation. One of the subjects of concern in the 2013 curriculum is the implementation of the ICT guidance program.

Based on Minister of Education and Culture Number 68 of 2014 explained the Role of ICT Teachers in schools that implement the 2013 curriculum. ICT teachers are given the task of providing knowledge about information and communication technology to students, teachers and other school components. ICT Teachers are obliged to guide students to be able to search data, process data, store, process and disseminate information using supporting learning tools. ICT teachers are also obliged to provide services and guidance to other subject teachers to conduct data searches, processing,

storing, presenting and disseminating information in order to make preparation, implementation and assessment of learning.

The implementation of the ICT guidance program aims to prepare students to be able to use increasingly developing technology. Students can use technology for the use of learning and information retrieval that supports the improvement of knowledge, skills and attitudes. The ICT guidance program is used as an effort to provide knowledge about the use of information and communication technology in accordance with the demands of 21st century development that technology knowledge connects all aspects of life. The use of technology in various aspects of life, requires education to provide facilities to use technology to be effective.

However, based on observations made at one of the Padang 8 Public Middle Schools, information was obtained that the implementation of the ICT guidance program was still not optimal. This is caused by the lack of learning resources used by the teacher and the absence of a clear reference to the material to be guided. The implementation of the ICT guidance program at SMP Negeri 8 Padang has not been fully in accordance with Permendikbud Number 45 of 2015 because ICT Teachers have not been able to carry out guidance to students because the implementation of guidance does not yet have a fixed schedule. Based on the results of the interview with one of the Padang N 8 Middle School teachers stated that during the ICT guidance program, the material presented was still unclear so that the assessment was still quite confusing.

The role of the ICT guidance program is also one of the supporting factors in the implementation of the 2013 curriculum. This is also in accordance with the demands of the 21st century where technological developments can encourage the availability of reliable and quality human resources. The school has the duty to provide intensive assistance to students. Students are expected to be able to choose and use technology according to their abilities, talents, and interests. The school also has a large responsibility for efforts to develop the learning progress of its students.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A. Evaluation

Evaluation is the determination of the value of a thing, which includes information used to decide the value of the success of a program, product, procedure, goal or benefit that is in the design of an alternative approach to maintain specific objectives. Evaluation is a process of providing information that can be used as material for consideration to determine the value and price of goals achieved, design, implementation and as a recommendation in making decisions, helping to account for and improve understanding of the phenomenon. So that evaluation can mean the provision of information that can be described as consideration in making decisions.

Arikunto and Jabar (2009: 1) ^[2] explain that evaluation activities are used to gather information about the activities that are used to determine the right solution in making decisions. Scriven in Stufflebeam and Shinkfield (2007: 369) ^[3] defines evaluation as: evaluation is the process of determining the merit, worth, and values of the products of the process. The process of determining the benefits and values of

an activity or program and evaluation is the product of the process. Next

Stufflebeam and Shinkfield (2007: 326) states that: evaluation is a systematic investigation of some object's value. Evaluation is an investigation, research, investigation or systematic examination of the value of an object. Operationally, Stufflebeam and Shinkfield (2007: 326) explain that evaluation is a process of planning, obtaining, reporting, and using descriptive information and considering several object benefits, value of significance and honesty in order to guide decision making, accountability, support, disseminate practices effective and increase understanding of the phenomena involved.

B. Program

Program is one component in a policy. The program is a plan that involves a series of activities carried out within a certain period of time that contain policies. Arikunto and Jabar (2009: 4) define the program as a union or unit of activity which is the realization or implementation of a policy, takes place in a continuous process and occurs in an organization involving a group of people.

Suharsimi Arikunto (2004: 2) the program can be understood in two ways, namely in general and specifically. General program curling is a plan or design of activities to be carried out by a person within a certain period of time. Whereas the definition of the program in particular is usually associated with evaluation which means a unit or unit of activity which is the implementation or realization of a policy, takes place in a continuous process and its implementation is carried out in an organization involving many people.

C. Evaluation Program

Program evaluation is a series that is carried out to find out the extent to which the goals and objectives of the program or project have been realized, provide information for decision making, compare performance with standards or benchmarks to find out gaps, assess price and quality and systematic investigation of the value or quality of an object. Program evaluation is a series of activities carried out intentionally to see the success of a program. Conducting program evaluation is an activity intended to find out how high the success rate of the planned activities (Suharsimi Arikunto, 2009: 297).

Arikunto and Jabar (2009: 1-2) explain that program evaluation is a unit or unit of activity that aims to gather information about the realization or implementation of a policy, takes place in a continuous process, and occurs in an organization involving a group of people to take decision. Furthermore, both of them argue that program evaluation is a series of activities carried out intentionally to see the success of the program. According to Tyler in Arikunto and Jabar (2009: 5) explained that program evaluation is a process carried out to find out whether the purpose of education has been realized.

D. CIPP (Contexts, Input, Process, Product)

The CIPP program evaluation model was developed by Stufflebeam where CIPP stands for Context, Input, Process and Product. Mulyatiningsih (2011: 126) [4] argues that CIPP

evaluation is known as formative evaluation with the aim of making decisions and improving programs. The CIPP model shows that the success of educational programs is influenced by various factors, such as the characteristics of students and the environment, the objectives of the program and the equipment used, procedures and mechanisms for implementing the program.

E. Curriculum

Wina Sanjaya (2006: 2)^[5] states that the curriculum is interpreted in three contexts, namely curriculum as a number of subjects, curriculum as learning experience and curriculum as planning learning programs. The curriculum as a number of subjects means that the curriculum contains standards that must be followed and achieved by students to achieve educational goals. The curriculum as a learning experience that is students participating in learning is the responsibility of the teacher or school but when students are in the school environment or outside the school environment based on educational activities that are followed by students.

The curriculum as a learning program planning is the teacher planning a learning program that is guided by the existing curriculum and developed in accordance with the characteristics of students so that students are able to achieve the set competencies. The curriculum according to Nasution (1995: 9)^[6] is a subject taught at school. Meanwhile, according to Oemar Hamalik (2001: 66)^[7] the curriculum is a set of plans and arrangements regarding the contents and materials of students and the methods used as guidelines for the implementation of teaching and learning activities.

The 2013 curriculum is an effort to simplify and be thematic-integrative in nature. The 2013 curriculum is prepared to create generations who are ready to face the challenges of the future. Because the curriculum is structured to anticipate future developments. The aim of the 2013 curriculum development according to the Ministry of Education and Culture is (Permendikbud No. 69 of 2013 concerning the Basic Framework and Curriculum Structure of Senior High Schools / Madrasah Aliyah)^[8] namely preparing Indonesian people to have the ability to live as individuals and citizens who are faithful, productive, creative, innovative and affective and able to contribute to the life of the world, nation, state and civilization.

F. Guidance TIK

Developing technology provides a great opportunity for the development of quality management education and learning processes in schools through the use of ICT. The use of ICT has been used in the field of education as a medium that helps teachers deliver information. Thus ICT has enormous potential to transform all aspects of education in schools to achieve learning goals. Therefore, the role of ICT teachers and KKPI teachers needs to be optimized in the implementation of the 2013 curriculum. ICT teachers and KKPI teachers in the implementation of the 2013 curriculum are functioned as ICT Teachers.

The ICT guidance program as a 2013 curriculum-based Pilot Project in accordance with Minister of Education and

Culture Regulation number 68 of 2014^[9] is an ICT guidance and facilitation program for students, fellow subject teachers and education staff in schools to utilize ICT as a source and / or learning facilities at school. The ICT guidance program can be implemented with classics or groups and individuals with ICT teacher workloads guiding at least 150 (one hundred and fifty) students per year in 1 (one) or more education units.

Article 2 of the Minister of Education and Culture Regulation No. 68 concerning the Role of ICT Teachers and KKPI states that ICT teachers must have a Bachelor (S-1) or four (D-IV) academic qualification in information technology and have a certificate in an ICT midwife or KKPI. To smooth the teaching and learning process Teachers use ICT as preparation, implementation, and assessment of learning so that it can be more effective in utilizing time. So, there needs to be guidance and facilitation from ICT teachers to other subject teachers so that they can utilize the existing technology well and maximally, besides that other subject teachers can gain experience in using technology in accordance with the times.

III. DEVELOPMENT METHOD

This research is evaluation research, which is a research activity to collect data, presents accurate and objective information about the implementation of ICT guidance programs in junior high schools (SMP) based on established criteria. The evaluation research model used in this study was CIPP. The study was conducted to evaluate the implementation of ICT Guidance activities carried out at the Padang city junior high school which included program planning, program implementation processes and the results / impacts of program implementation. The selection of the CIPP method is because the one studied is related to the program or system being run. The evaluation of the CIPP model in this study will be elaborated into four steps, namely: evaluation of context, input, process, product.

This research was carried out at the Padang City Public Middle School which implemented the ICT Guidance Program in the odd semester of the 2018/2019 academic year. The research subject is an object or person where the data of the research variable are inherent and which is at issue (Arikunto, 1993: 116). So, the subject is something very important, because on the subject there are data about variables that will be examined and observed by researchers. In this study the subject of research is that all parties involved in the implementation of the ICT Guidance program include educators, students, principals and other related parties.

IV. EVALUATION RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Evaluation Result

The results of this study were obtained through interviews with principals, vice principals, ICT guidance teachers, and students. Interviews were conducted to obtain in-depth information on how the curriculum context runs in Padang City Public Middle School, how to input in the ICT guidance program, how the ICT guidance program process took place,

and how the results of the ICT guidance program run in Padang City Public Middle School.

In addition, the information obtained through the interviews was also carried out verification and confirmation through the existing observation and documentation related to the ICT guidance program. The following will describe the results of research obtained based on the context, input, process, and results as follows:

1. Evaluation Contexts

ICT guidance is one of the guidance programs implemented to improve the ability of students and teachers to use information and communication technology used in the learning process. The ICT guidance program is carried out in schools by providing knowledge about the use of ICT. Based on the facts encountered in the field, observations and documentation of the learning program were conducted

Based on the results of the research carried out, the curriculum policies implemented in high-category schools have actively implemented ICT guidance programs by conducting scheduled ICT guidance programs in the school hours applicable in this case are SMP 1, SMPN 8 and SMPN 31. Schools which is included in the moderate category in this case SMP 24, SMP 25 and SMP 6 have not implemented a fully scheduled TIK guidance program because the implementation of an ICT guidance program is carried out alternately with counseling. While the curriculum policy that applies to schools in the low category in this case is SMP 23, SMP 27 and SMP 28 have not implemented a scheduled guidance program so that the program implementation process is carried out outside of learning activities.

Based on the results of the research conducted, the need for schools is to organize guidance programs in a structured manner according to the curriculum that can increase the knowledge of school members in the use of ICT in schools. The physical condition of the school environment supports the implementation of the ICT guidance program. The ICT guidance process is carried out in a structured manner with a clear guidance schedule so that the guidance process can be carried out properly.

2. Evaluation Input

The characteristics of students found in schools in the high category have a high interest in the use of information and communication technology. This can be seen from the intensity of the use of labor by students is very high. Learning activities and guidance are well followed so that the ICT guidance process is carried out in accordance with the planned program. Schools in the medium and low categories have the same characteristics of students which also have a high interest in the use of information and communication technology except that the use of technology is still limited to using gadgets for some activities that are not in accordance with ICT guidance material.

Education in the input perspective has knowledge about the use of ICT and can make guidance programs that are in accordance with the characteristics of students. The ICT guidance teacher has the ability as a professional teacher in carrying out guidance and explaining material in the ICT field. The schools that were sampled in this study have made efforts

to provide professional teachers in the ICT field.

The characteristics of ICT guidance teachers include guidance teacher education, the ability to manage BTIK services, classroom management, skills in using ICT in implementing guidance, managing interactions well in implementing guidance. based on observations and documentation in the school it can be seen that the process of implementing ICT guidance is carried out by computer education graduate teachers.

The teacher participates in the discussion of ICT subject teachers to increase knowledge about the use of ICTs and share information on how to implement ICT programs in their respective schools. All junior high school teachers participated in this activity, including schools which were sampled in this study.

Schools that are included in the medium and high category have adequate facilities in the implementation of ICT guidance programs. This can be seen from the number of computers the school has is sufficient for ICT guidance program activities. While schools in the low category have not had adequate facilities due to the lack of computers that can be used by students when the ICT guidance process is carried out.

3. Evaluation Process

Teachers of ICT guidance programs design, facilitate, coordinate guidance programs so that they can be used as a means to develop students' potential. Process evaluation is needed to determine the extent to which the plan has been implemented and the components that need to be improved. In this study it was found that the ICT guidance teacher had carried out the guidance well where the teacher delivered the material using methods and sources of learning in accordance with the guidance material.

The teacher plans guidance by using language that is easily understood by students so that the guidance process is very active, except that the guidance time is very limited so the learning process is less than optimal at each meeting. The teacher has the skills to ask questions that can increase students' attention in following the guidance process. in this study, process evaluation includes student activities and teacher activities. In the high category schools students seemed very enthusiastic in following the guidance process. the teacher delivers the material using polite language and can be understood by students. Students feel happy following the guidance process.

The results of observations in the medium and low school categories of student activities are quite good because there are still students doing activities outside the guidance material so that the guidance process is slightly disturbed. Only some students respond to the questions asked by the teacher. Students use computers to play games.

The teacher helps students in self-development activities. Teacher activities observed during the guidance process are the ability of the teacher to carry out guidance in a classical and individual manner as well as the teacher in conveying information about ICT. Teachers in high category schools and are conducting structured individual and group guidance so that guidance activities can be measured. In low category schools the implementation of guidance is still not structured

because there is no clear schedule for the implementation of ICT guidance.

4. Evaluation Product

Product evaluation of the ICT guidance program includes the achievements achieved by students both in academic and non academic fields in conducting guidance. product evaluation ICT guidance to what extent ICT guidance produces the desired output. Guidance products are generated from the implementation of guidance in an appropriate, ideal, and proportional manner so that the teacher must have the ability to explain the theory contained in the guidance material.

B. Discussion

Context evaluation is a description and specification of the program environment, needs that have not been met, population characteristics and samples of individuals served and program objectives. To get the desired results, of course requires careful planning and formulating programs in improving the quality of students in understanding and increasing understanding of the use of ICTs. Context evaluation helps plan decisions, determine the needs to be achieved by the program and formulate program objectives. Program planning and formulation are tailored to the characteristics of students.

The input evaluation activity aims to help organize decisions, determine the sources, alternatives to be taken, what plans and strategies to achieve needs, and how to guide procedures to achieve them. The characteristics of students found in schools in the high category have a high interest in the use of information and communication technology. This can be seen from the intensity of the use of labor by students is very high. Learning activities and guidance are well followed so that the ICT guidance process is carried out in accordance with the planned program.

Product evaluation of the ICT guidance program includes the achievements achieved by students both in academic and non academic fields in conducting guidance. product evaluation ICT guidance to what extent ICT guidance produces the desired output. Guidance products are generated from the implementation of guidance in an appropriate, ideal, and proportional manner so that the teacher must have the ability to explain the theory contained in the guidance material.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion, it can be concluded that the ICT guidance program at Padang City Junior High School. Then the conclusion of each stage of the evaluation is as follows:

1. The konteks component includes curriculum policies, school needs and the school climate in good categories. Schools that are included in the medium category in this case are SMP 24, SMP 25 and SMP 6 have not implemented a fully-scheduled ICT guidance program because the implementation of ICT guidance programs is carried out alternately with counseling. While the curriculum policy that applies to schools in the low category in this case is SMP 23, SMP 27 and SMP 28 have

not implemented a scheduled guidance program so that the process of implementing the program is carried out outside of learning activities.

2. The Input component includes the characteristics of students who take part in the program, the support of the school, the characteristics of ICT guidance teachers and infrastructure facilities. Schools in the low category have not had adequate facilities due to the lack of computers that can be used by students during the ICT guidance process.
3. The component of the ICT guidance program process includes the activities of teachers and students when conducting guidance. High category schools get an average yield of 0.81 which is in the good category. For the category schools, the average results are 0.79 which includes the very good category. Whereas for low category schools, the average yield is 0.75 which includes the very good category.
4. Product components are already in good category. The achievement of the ICT guidance program is in accordance with the targets set by the school. The program created by the teacher is very effective for monitoring and measuring the success of the guidance program.

REFERENCES

- [1] Fadillah, M. 2014. Implementasi Kurikulum 2013 Dalam Pembelajaran SD/MI, SD/MTS, dan SMA/MA. Penerbit: Ar-Ruzz, Yogyakarta.
- [2] Arikunto, Suharsimi dan Cepi Abdul Jabar, Safrudin. 2009. Evaluasi Program Pendidikan. Penerbit: Bumi Aksara, Jakarta
- [3] L.Stufflebeam, Daniel and Anthony J.Shinkfield, 2007, Evaluation Theory, Models, and Applications, San Francisco: A Wiley Imprint
- [4] Mulyaningsih, Endang. 2012. Metode Penelitian Terapan Bidang Pendidikan. Yogyakarta: Alfabeta.
- [5] Wina Sanjaya. 2006. Strategi Pembelajaran. Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group.
- [6] Nasution. 1995. Dikdaktik Asas-asas Mengajar. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara
- [7] Hamalik, Oemar. 2008. Kurikulum dan Pembelajaran. Penerbit : Bumi Aksara, Jakarta
- [8] Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Republik Indonesia Nomor 69 Tahun 2013, Jakarta.
- [9] Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Republik Indonesia Nomor 68 Tahun 2014 Tentang Peran Guru Teknologi Informasi dan Komunikasi dan Guru Keterampilan Komputer dan Pengelolaan Informasi dalam Implementasi Kurikulum 2013, Jakarta.